

Decontamination of (Methoxy Methyl Phosphoryl) Oxymethane (MMPOM) over Nano-Structured Co_3O_4 and MnCo_2O_4 Catalysts

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Abstract

In the present study, the practicality of catalytic surfaces of nano-structured Co_3O_4 and MnCo_2O_4 for the adsorption and neutralization reactions of organo-phosphorous pollutants has been investigated. Co_3O_4 and MnCo_2O_4 nanoparticles have been successfully prepared by precipitation method using cadmium nitrate and manganese nitrate as the precursors and then characterized by scanning electron microscopy-energy dispersive micro-analysis (SEM-EDX) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) techniques. The application of the synthesized nanoparticles as solid catalysts for the adsorption and neutralization of (methoxy methyl phosphoryl) oxymethane (MMPOM) as an agricultural organo-phosphorous pesticide was assayed in different solvents and monitored by phosphorous-31 nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy ($^{31}\text{PNMR}$), gas chromatography-mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) and IR analyses. The experimental results have shown that 39%, 47% and 62% of MMPOM have been removed on the surface of $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4\text{NPs}$ in isopropanol, chloroform and decane solvents after 12 h, respectively. While, higher amounts (80%, 92% and 100%) were removed in the same solvents, when $\text{MnCo}_2\text{O}_4\text{NPs}$ were chosen as the catalytic surface. This demonstrates that the choice of nanoparticle and solvent ($\text{MnCo}_2\text{O}_4\text{NPs}$ and decane) have a great impact on the detoxification of MMPOM.

Keywords: Co_3O_4 nanoparticles; MnCo_2O_4 nanoparticles; precipitation; (methoxy methyl phosphoryl) oxymethane (MMPOM); adsorption; neutralization.